

БАРКАМОЛ ЁШЛАР КЕЛАЖАГИМИЗ ПОЙДЕВОРИ.

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БухМТИ “Ижтимоий фанлар” кафедраси ўқитувчиси

Аннотация: Мақолада юртимизда ёшларнинг интеллектуал ва ижодий салоҳиятини мустаҳкамлаш, уларнинг мамлакатимиз учун етук ва баркамол кадрлар қилиб тарбиялаш ҳақида тўхталиб ўтилган. Ёшларимизнинг маънавий жасорати аввало уларнинг ўз юртига, халқига бўлган муҳаббати ва садоқатида, мустақиллик тақдири учун фидойилик кўрсатиб ва масъулигини ҳис этишида намоён бўлиши такидланган.

Калит сўзлар: Ижтимоий ҳаёт, комил инсон, иймон, маърифат, ҳақиқат, сабр-тоқат, маънавий ҳаёт, баркамол инсон.

ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ МОЛОДЕЖЬ – ФУНДАМЕНТ НАШЕГО БУДУЩЕГО.

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена укреплению интеллектуального и творческого потенциала молодежи нашей страны, воспитанию ее, чтобы стать зрелыми и всесторонне развитыми кадрами для нашей страны. Подчеркнуто, что духовное мужество нашей молодежи выражается, прежде всего, в их любви и преданности своей стране и народу, в их преданности и чувстве ответственности за судьбы независимости.

Ключевые слова: Общественная жизнь, совершенный человек, вера, просвещение, истина, терпение, духовная жизнь, совершенный человек.

IDEOLOGICAL YOUTH IS THE FOUNDATION OF OUR FUTURE.

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Annotation: *The article focuses on strengthening the intellectual and creative potential of young people in our country, educating them to become mature and well-rounded personnel for our country. It was emphasized that the spiritual courage of our youth is first of all reflected in their love and devotion to their country and people, their devotion and sense of responsibility for the fate of independence.*

Keywords: *Social life, perfect man, faith, enlightenment, truth, patience, spiritual life, perfect man.*

In the history of mankind, spirituality has always served the perfection of man, the preservation and strengthening of the nation's identity, and the healthy development of society. Great work is being done in our country to strengthen the intellectual and creative potential of young people, to increase their involvement in the ongoing reforms in our country. After all, one of the most important tasks today is to bring up well-rounded, purposeful and energetic young people with modern knowledge and skills, who can take responsibility for the decent future of the country. In the current context of globalization, the urgency of cultivating loyalty to the national idea, patriotism, high spiritual and moral views, the formation of ideological and spiritual immunity in a wide range of people, especially young people, is growing.

Because in the world, information attacks, ideological and spiritual threats under the guise of popular culture are growing. Spirituality is a powerful force in protecting our country and our youth from such ideological and spiritual attacks and evil forces.

The process of educating young people in the spirit of spiritual courage is multifaceted and is shaped by the influence of many factors. One of such factors is the owners of great and incomparable spiritual courage, goodness and enlightenment, freedom fighters, commanders, statesmen, their exemplary ways of life. Examples include Musa Khorezmi and Ahmad Fergani, who worked at the Bayt ul-Hikma (House of Wisdom) in Baghdad; Abu Nasr ibn Iraq, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Mahmud Khojandi, who worked at the Khorezm Mamun Academy; Mirzo Ulugbek, Qazizoda Rumi, Ali Kushchi and others who worked at the Samarkand (Ulugbek) Academy left an indelible mark on the history of science in the Middle Ages with their unparalleled discoveries, showing an example of spiritual courage.

Educating our youth in a high spiritual and moral spirit, forming in them a sense of spiritual courage is an important factor in protecting them from various ideological and spiritual threats. Courage is a spiritual and moral

phenomenon that shows that everyone has reached a high level of maturity. It is a category of spirituality, which means that a person, including our youth, protects the interests of society and its members, preserves independence, strengthens it, devotes himself to a particular task, fully mobilizes all his strength and capabilities.

The spiritual courage of our youth is manifested, first of all, in their love and devotion to their country and people, in their devotion and sense of responsibility for the fate of independence.

The process of educating young people in the spirit of spiritual courage is multifaceted and is shaped by the influence of many factors. One of such factors is the owners of great and incomparable spiritual courage, goodness and enlightenment, freedom fighters, commanders, statesmen, their exemplary ways of life. Examples include Musa Khorezmi and Ahmad Fergani, who worked at the Bayt ul-Hikma (House of Wisdom) in Baghdad; Abu Nasr ibn Iraq, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Mahmud Khojandi, who worked at the Khorezm Mamun Academy; Mirzo Ulugbek, Qazizoda Rumi, Ali Kushchi and others who worked at the Samarkand (Ulugbek) Academy left an indelible mark on the history of science in the Middle Ages with their unparalleled discoveries, showing an example of spiritual courage.

It is an expression of their true spiritual courage that our young people are selfless every day, at every moment, tirelessly and tirelessly mobilize themselves for the great creative goals that they have set for themselves. In various dangerous situations and threats in life, the nation represents the content of the concept of courage to mobilize itself to take disaster, even if it is voluntarily, consciously risking its life for the benefit of the homeland. Spiritual courage is not realized in exchange for material or spiritual interests, but it also reflects the noble deeds of man, including our youth, who have dedicated their lives, goals and aspirations to the people and society. Spiritual courage is a spiritual quality that is possible not only for the potential of individuals and individuals, but also for everyone, including our youth.

If we look at the history of the world and humanity, great people with a strong sense of spiritual courage in their hearts and souls will not spare themselves in the pursuit of justice and truth, freedom, science, enlightenment in any complex and dangerous situation, for the freedom of the country, who have done exemplary, instructive work that will be an example to all.

The process of educating young people in the spirit of spiritual courage is multifaceted and is shaped by the influence of many factors. One of such factors is the owners of great and incomparable spiritual courage, goodness

and enlightenment, freedom fighters, commanders, statesmen, their exemplary ways of life. Enlightened and selfless people such as Cholpon, Qodiri, Usman Nasir, who sacrificed their personal interests and well-being for the benefit of the people and carried the ideas of independence, are also an example of spiritual courage. Inculcating the above into the minds and psyche of our youth will lead them to spiritual courage. The task of our youth is to learn from the above and contribute to the preservation and further strengthening of the achieved independence.

In short, inculcating the above into the minds and psyche of our youth will lead them to spiritual courage. The task of our youth is to learn from the above and contribute to the preservation and further strengthening of the achieved independence.

Concluding from the above views, we must all feel responsible for the upbringing of young people and work together to combat the evils that are not unique to our society. Youth is the future of any society. The struggle for destructive and enlightening ideas for their consciousness continues. In this ideological struggle, the winner is the side that has justified the confidence of the youth with its noble practical actions. After all, a harmoniously developed generation and high-moral patriotic youth are the real successors of today and tomorrow.

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